

Synthetic load profiles of non-energy intensive industrial sites: A combined bottom-up and top-down approach

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ABSTRACT

The heterogeneous nature of the industrial sector in terms of process and product variety often hinders assessments of its energy consumption. The generation of synthetic load profiles (LPs) however offers a key instrument to support energy suppliers, grid operators and industries themselves by quickly evaluating the impacts of energy efficiency measures, fuel switch, new technologies etc. Currently, such LP generators are only developed for single real-life industry plants or require comprehensive beforehand data. Within this study, we propose a new model for generating synthetic LPs of industrial process chains without the need for extensive, plant-specific data. This solution includes a series of bottom-up and top-down approaches. We analyse different data sources and develop algorithms based on underlying data science methods and technical and economical modelling paradigms like Markov chains or Economy of Scale. Here, we describe novel findings e.g., a method that proves the prediction of industrial shift models from a top-down perspective or effects on the energy demand of industrial plants for rising production capacities. Furthermore, we prove that only some production processes in industrial facilities are responsible for the main share of their energy demand, as the residues can be modelled by numerical analyses. We validate the developed approach by generating synthetic electricity LPs of different real-life industrial plants and comparing the results to measured LPs. This study contains five case studies, of which we found valid approximations of our synthetic LPs to the measured, real-life plants. However, our model's results differ from measured LPs, especially when depicting lower energy demands (< 200 kW). Furthermore, long-term periodicities e.g., part-time working hours on Saturdays have not been incorporated into our model yet, which leads to certain inaccuracies. We quantified these effects within this study. This, nevertheless, leaves open areas for future research work.

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1. Introduction

The modern energy system is confronted with significant challenges. The climate crisis presents itself as one of the most fundamental humanitarian crises. However, the fast-increasing rate of the implementation of renewable energies heavily influences the volatility of supplied energies and therefore the stability of the overall energy system [1].

In the age of digitalisation, we can deem ourselves lucky enough to hold the needed means to develop fruit-bearing solutions for solving these challenges. Energy system models play a vital role in this context, especially for energy suppliers and grid operators. These instruments support the strategic decision-making for the energy transition by incorporating topical trends

and technologies and swiftly evaluating their impact on the physical energy and grid system [2].

As the European industry is accountable for around 20% of the gross inland energy consumption [3], it has to take a major part in the energy transition. Whereas the development of energy models in the mobility and residential sectors is well underway, industrial models are lagging behind in terms of their dynamic and comprehensive character [4]. To accelerate this process, our motivation lies in proposing novel approaches to depict the dynamic demand and generation behaviour of single industrial sites in terms of timely high-resolved load profiles (LPs) as we therefore can introduce new aspects and improvements to global energy system models. As we already demonstrated a model for energy intensive industries in our preceding study [5], we now want to address the depiction of the more complex, non-energy intensive industries like Machinery, Food & Beverages etc. The generation of LPs for the mentioned industries will therefore be the main topic of this study.

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List of Acronyms

LP	Load Profile
DSM	Demand Side Management
IAC	Industrial Assessment Center
kWh	Kilo Watt Hours
MWh	Mega Watt Hours
TWh	Terra Watt Hours
e.g.	Exempli Gratia
NACE	Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne
IEA	International Energy Agency
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
P	Power/Energy Demand
E	Energy Consumption
t	Tonnes
min	Minutes
h	Hour
SEC	Specific Energy Consumption
EOS	Economy Of Scale
LF	Load Factor
MAPE	Mean Average Percentage Error
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transformation
GUI	Graphic User Interface

1.1. State of research

In our preceding study [5], we discussed recent developments in modelling methodologies, which allow the depiction of dynamic consumption patterns and therefore generation of LPs of consumers and consumer groups in the mobility [4] and residential sectors. In the latter, for example, a comprehensive model by Pflugradt and Muntwyler [6] was developed, generating LPs of single households based on residential behaviour and consumption of household appliances. This bottom-up methodology can be applied to design local energy systems, for which simple standardised LPs are deemed too inaccurate [7].

Our findings show that several models for the industrial sector have been developed to statically determine their energy consumption [5]. This allows the investigation of e.g. long-term emission reduction or the utilisation of renewable energies [8]. However, timely high-resolved synthetic LP generation represents a key solution for evaluating future grid demands, scheduling energy supply, or implementing demand-side management (DSM) measures.

Based on the literature research in our preceding study, we further investigated existing modelling approaches for generating LPs of industrial sites. We found only a few, which we classified in Fig. 1 depending on their systemic application (thermal LP, electric LP, multi-energy LP) and methodology (bottom-up, top-down). We also assessed how many industrial subsectors can be depicted by the proposed approach without relying on additional, external data (user-wise) or real-life measurements.

Sandhaas et al. (A) [9] developed a top-down methodology, to model electricity LPs based on normalised daily LPs of five industrial subsectors. These normalised LPs were divided into eight end-use applications (useful energy categories) such as mechanical drive, lighting, heating etc. The fraction of allocation of the useful energy categories to the resulting electricity LP was defined by investigating industrial databases. LP fluctuations were introduced via the application of stochastics. The generation

of thermal LPs was not covered within this work, which certainly is another major field of application due to the high rate of industrial, thermal consumers [16].

Jesper et al. (B) [10] created a methodology for generating thermal LPs by analysing real measured data from more than 6 industrial subsectors via k-Means clustering and regression analysis. They found strong evidence that – unlike electricity loads – industrial, thermal LPs are partly following ambient temperatures. This effect can also be observed for residential homes in the private sector. Similar analysis methods like Jesper et al. were conducted by Richard et al. (C) [11] to identify DSM measures and by Dedić et al. (E) [13] for small and medium-sized enterprises. The latter study also includes examinations on working days (distinction of different working days and holidays) and their implications on LPs. Valdes and Camargo (D) [12] also investigated real measured LPs, however, they did not utilise k-Means clustering.

Dock et al. (F) [14] developed a bottom-up method for generating electrical and thermal LPs of production lines of the Iron & Steel subsector. Their model is based upon real-life measurements of major process units like the electric arc furnace or the ladle furnaces. The corresponding LPs are generated by using Markov chains.

Thiede et al. (G) [15] offer a generic energy flow-oriented manufacturing simulation. Through this bottom-up approach, DSM and energy efficiency measures on factory level can be derived. This model can be applied to different industrial sites and incorporates detailed process control schemes and economic assessments. However, the applied methodology relies on comprehensive measurements and production chain knowledge on-site beforehand.

Within our preceding study (H) [5] we developed a methodology for depicting LPs of energy intensive subsectors. We found that energy intensive industries “exhibit a limited range of varying production processes and principles” [5]. Based on this finding, we developed a bottom-up approach supported by top-down algorithms incorporating the simulation of production lines via discrete event simulation. Throughout this study, we covered the main production lines of the subsectors Iron & Steel, Paper & Pulp, Chemical and Non-Metallic Minerals, defined by the International Energy Agency (IEA) [17].

A summary table compares the investigations of this study to the mentioned past research works in more detail, see Appendix.

1.2. Research hypotheses and structure of this paper

Based on the literature review above, we conclude that the first important groundwork for generating LPs of selected industrial subsectors has been laid out successfully. However, we found major open research areas, especially regarding the methodology’s comprehensiveness and scope for covering the entire industrial sector and more than one energy carrier. The goal of this study is to extend our existing approach by developing a methodology for covering the more complex, non-energy intensive subsectors like Machinery or Food & Beverages as well. To reach this goal we situate the following hypotheses:

- Non-energy intensive industries apply a wider range of production paradigms and processes compared to energy intensive industries. Sole bottom-up models will fail to reach the mentioned goal because of the great scope of vital data while the results of sole top-down models are too undetailed. The conducted literature review, as the main results are stated above and in Fig. 1, supports this hypothesis

Fig. 1. Assessment of developed models for generating industrial LPs: (A) Sandhaas et al. 2022 [9], (B) Jesper et al. 2021 [10], (C) Richard et al. 2017 [11], (D) Valdes and Camargo 2021 [12], (E) Dedić et al. 2022 [13], (F) Dock et al. 2021 [14], (G) Thiede et al. 2022 [15], (H) Binderbauer et al. 2022 [5] ; See summary table in Appendix for more details of these literature studies.

by demonstrating that either single energy carriers are included in the shown top-down methodologies or multi-energy carrier methodologies are developed by incorporating extensive databases for a bottom-up approach. A combined bottom-up and top-down approach will adequately depict these industrial subsectors without relying on extensive process-specific data but covering multi-energy systems, nevertheless.

- The applied shift models at real industrial sites influence the energy demand and generation pattern of industrial sites strongly. Hernández et al. [18] investigate the impact of working days and weekends or holidays on electrical LPs, however, did not examine the fluctuating behaviour during working days (production and non-production times) for other energy carriers as well.
- The energy consumption behaviour of industries during peak times can be traced back to a limited amount of energy intensive process units. We assume that this behaviour already determined the energy demand in energy intensive industries [5], which can also be seen in the non-energy intensive sectors as well.
- The microeconomics paradigm of Economy of Scale can be applied to assess the energy consumption of industrial plants.

We will prove these hypotheses throughout this study as we thoroughly assess the non-energy intensive subsectors in Section 2. Therefore, an overview of the developed methodology will be presented first and explained in a detailed manner in the following subsections. Of these, Section 2.1 includes the handling of input variables for the model, followed by the explanation of our shift model calculator (Section 2.2). Regarding the bottom-up approach within this study, we developed a dynamic Markov-chain model for integrating the energy-consuming behaviour of energy intensive production processes (Section 2.3). In Section 2.4, our approach for assessing weekly consumption and demand of industrial plants based upon Economy of Scale is described. These models are complemented by a load factor analysis and

a comprehensive iterative algorithm in Section 2.5. To evaluate the functionality of our approach, Section 3 contains five conducted case studies, which are described and analysed extensively. Finally, Section 4 concludes this study, by reflecting on the hypotheses stated above.

2. Methodology

The distinction between energy intensive and non-energy intensive industrial subsectors varies slightly depending on legislators and their systemic interpretation. The European Commission denotes subsectors as energy intensive if certain processes are included within the production line. Such processes are for example electrolyser units, chemical reduction processes, processes for metal production or glass fabrication etc. [19]. In our preceding study, we pointed out the characteristics of these subsectors. However, this developed approach finds its limitations when it comes to non-energy intensive subsectors:

Fig. 2 shows that non-energy intensive subsectors account for around 28% of the total energy consumption in Austria of 135 TWh [16]. Even though this share is rather small compared to energy intensive industries, further analysis in terms of employment and gross value-added shows that non-energy intensive subsectors take a bigger role within the overall industrial landscape, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Additionally, we can conclude that the product and process variety of these subsectors is much more comprehensive than in energy intensive industries. This can easily be derived when examining the European NACE classification, which categorises the IEA-defined subsectors in more detail by introducing a graduated system [21] : For example “C 16.2.1 – Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based-panels” is a part of “C 16 – Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork”, which can be assigned to the IEA subsector “Wood & Wood Products”. While non-energy intensive industries make up 149 of the product-specific 4-digit NACE classes, energy intensive subsectors only account for 65 [20]. It can be reasoned that these products’ extensive subsectors can be covered either by deploying new simulation methodologies or providing a comprehensive database, even larger than for energy intensive industries. Our

Fig. 2. Comparison of energy intensive and non-energy intensive industrial subsectors regarding total energy consumption [16], the total number of employees and gross value added for 2019 [20] ; *Non-Ferrous Metals is part of the energy intensive industry, however, due to the small share of primary non-ferrous metal production in comparison to secondary in Austria, we classified this sector as non-energy intensive.

motivation however lies in the depiction of LPs for industrial sites via an efficient and user-friendly methodology without the need for individualised, beforehand data (e.g., measurements on site).

Prominent industrial databases along these classifications utilised in this study are for example ETS (Emission trading system) database, EMAS (Eco Management and Audit Scheme) database, EuroStat and IAC database.

Our literature review shows that top-down methodologies mainly cover the generation of LPs for single energy carriers (see Fig. 1). Bottom-up methods depict more than one energy carrier, however, require a more extensive, site-specific database. We conclude that top-down models rely on the site's sole electricity or natural gas metering for energy suppliers but manage to cover more industrial subsectors, while bottom-up models build up on underlying processes and consumption of various and internally produced energy carriers like steam. Thus, our developed methodology incorporates both top-down approaches to maximise the number of targeted subsectors and bottom-up approaches to increase the LP depiction of selected energy carriers.

Fig. 3 depicts the developed methodology for generating representative synthetic LPs of fictitious and non-fictitious industrial sites of selected non-energy intensive subsectors. The methodology can be divided into five partaking algorithms which we will discuss in the following chapters in detail.

The following databases are incorporated into the methodology:

- Herold Business Database [22] : This database contains information on site and NACE subsector-specific employment of companies in Austria including over 400 000 data points.
- Industrial Assessment Center (IAC) Database [23] : This database involves surveys of site and NACE subsector-specific information on employment, energy demand, production hours and capacity in the U.S. containing around 20 000 data points. The programme IAC is funded by the US Department of Energy (DOE).
- Useful Energy Analysis by Statistics Austria [24] : This classification lists the final energy demand on the IEA subsector level in Austria.

For generating synthetic LPs for fictitious or non-fictitious sites of non-energy intensive industries, the number of employees, selection of a specific NACE subsector and the production capacity

act as primary input parameters by the user (a). By determining the employment information and NACE classification the most probable deployed shift model is identified (b). To generate the production activity during the defined shift model, we developed a dynamic Markov model (c). The result is an unscaled LP reflecting the most energy intensive processes from the Markov model. This LP is then scaled within an iterative algorithm to meet the statistically determined plant characteristics from an Economy of Scale model (d).

We incorporated this methodology in an open access, free-to-use software called *Ganymed*, where we already implemented the generation of LPs of energy intensive industries from our preceding study [5].

2.1. Methodology input factors

The first part of the proposed methodology, as shown in Fig. 3 (a), covers the initial input information for setting up an industrial site. This information contains the selected NACE industrial subsector, to which the site can be assigned, the production capacity (e.g., t/h) and the number of production employees of the site. The number of employees can be either defined by the user deterministically or via stochastic distribution of analysed, single companies from Herold Business Database [22]. For the latter option, we developed a dedicated fit algorithm, which approximates the subsector-specific data by a power function. The probability densities of all considered data points from Herold Business Database act as regression points for the fit as depicted in Fig. 5 (b).

When the user chooses the stochastic option for determining the number of employees in the selected NACE subsector, the algorithm draws a random number z as a result of the cumulative distribution function. This random number z is outputted by a pseudo-random number generator, which is developed based on the logic of Mersenne-Twister. Through determining z , a possible number of employees for the manufacturing plant can be calculated stochastically as the yellow arrow indicates.

Fig. 4 shows an exemplary application of this stochastic assessment for the subsector "NACE 25 – Manufacture of fabricated metal products". The Herold Business Database presents 1314 individual Austrian industrial plants with their respective number of employees for this sector. We calculated an average employment number of 21 employees per plant. The Structural Business Statistics by Statistic Austria [20] also states the average number

Fig. 3. Overall LP generation methodology: (a) Input variables, (b) Algorithm to calculate the applied shift model with the highest probability, (c) Bottom-up model of dynamic Markov chains incorporating most energy intensive processes, (d) Regression model based upon Economy of Scale, (e) Iteration algorithm for scaling generated LPs, (f) Generated LPs.

Fig. 4. (a) Cumulative density and (b) Probability density functions NACE subsectors: NACE 25.6.1 - Treatment and coating of metals.

of employees for all subsectors. Thus, the calculated average can be justified by the report by Statistic Austria, which reveals 20 employees for the mentioned subsector. This can be deemed as the first satisfactory correspondence of our investigations. The histogram analysis in Fig. 4 (b) presents the probability densities of the collected 1314 data points. We limited the x-axis of the figure to 48 employees. The corresponding fit function for the cumulative density function from Fig. 4 (a) is given by the following formula:

$$x = e^{\left(\frac{f(x)-0.0227}{0.2385}\right)} \quad (1)$$

In this formula, $f(x)$ equals the randomly drawn number z between 0 and 1 (0% and 100%) as the input parameter to calculate the number of employees x based upon the regression function.

To prove an adequate regression fit of assumed normally distributed data points, we conducted a statistical t-test [25]. Here, we transferred the probability densities from (b) into a logarithmic plot. The corresponding fit can now be investigated on a linear relationship, for which we set a significance level α of $\alpha = 0.05$. The test shows a P -value of $P = 0.02$, which is lower than the significance level α . The hypothesis of normally distributed data points around the linear fit function in the logarithmic plot and, thus, correlation in Fig. 4 (b) can be accepted. We note that we investigated every NACE subsector on statistical significance.

2.2. Shift model algorithm

Based on real-life measurements and the analysis of industrial LPs, Dehning et al. [26] found a dependency of plant-specific LPs on the implemented shift models at the site. The authors classified phases, where the main production during the daily shift takes place, as “production times” and phases outside of shift times as “non-production times”. We reason that during the phase of production, energy consumption is higher than during non-production. In conclusion, the knowledge of the shift model being used is vital for generating LPs of the corresponding industrial site.

In the first step, we assumed that the applied real-life shift model depends on the specific NACE subsector and company size. Sen [27] examined this on yearly production hours from the IAC

Database [23] via a histogram analysis. The author found elevated peaks of yearly production hours directly corresponding to the mean value of weekly working hours of major shift model groups. Furthermore, the study defined upper and lower working hour limits for these proposed shift model groups. We identified these shift model groups to be also sufficient for depicting European shift models. However, we altered some of the proposed working hour limits to meet European standards e.g. according to statutory vacation days or maximum amount of working hours per week [28]. The defined shift model groups are listed in Table 1.

Next, Sen [27] concluded and proved that industrial subsectors apply these shift models varyingly. Based on these findings we examined each NACE subsector by the proposed working hours and related shift models from Table 1. Fig. 5 (b) shows a scatter plot of the number of employees and applied production hours of real-life industrial plants of the subsector NACE 16.1.0 in the IAC Database. We marked the working hour ranges of identified shift model groups with different colours accordingly and analysed the data points within these ranges via probabilistic analyses. The results of these analyses are probability density functions as shown in Fig. 5 (a). These subsector-specific density functions enable the determination of the most probable applied shift model for a certain company size or selected number of employees. For example, in the subsector NACE 16.1.0 the probabilistic analysis, as depicted in Fig. 5, show that a company with 100 production employees will apply shift model A of 40 h/week followed by shift model B of 80 h/week. For higher numbers of employees, the application of shift model B becomes more likely. For over, in this case, 600 employees, a stochastic determination is not possible anymore due to the small number of representative data points at these values. For these special cases, the to-be-depicted industrial site should be divided into production areas (e.g., assembling, coating, etc.), which are then treated as single sites. As the information of the number of employees is generated out of the approach, we have discussed in Fig. 3 (a), typical production and non-production times based upon shift models for generating the according LP can be assessed.

Fig. 5. Examination of “NACE 16.1.0 – Sawmilling and planing of wood”: (a) Probability density functions of all shift model groups, (b) Scatter plot showing employment and applied production hours of industrial plants along with defined working hour ranges of defined shift model groups. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 1
Classification of shift models via shift model groups including their applied working hours and limits.

Shift Model Groups	Shift Model	Upper Limit	Lower Limit
Group A: 40 h/week	8 h / 5 days – Single Shift	52 h/week (assuming a maximum of 12 h/shift)	37.5 h/week (assuming 7.5 h/shift)
Group B: 80 h/week	16 h / 5 days – Two Shifts	104 h/week (assuming a maximum of 12 h/shift)	75 h/week (assuming 7.5 h/shift)
Group C: 120 h/week	24 h / 5 days – Three Shifts	120 h/week	112.5 h/week (assuming 7.5 h/shift)
	20 h / 6 days – Two Shifts		
Group D: 144 h/week	24 h / 6 days – Three Shifts	144 h/week	135 h/week (assuming 7.5 h/shift)
	20 h / 7 days – Two Shifts		
Group E: 168 h/week	24 h / 7 days – continuous	168 h/week or 8760 h/year	160 h/week

2.3. Dynamic Markov model

Our previously presented algorithms are the sole top-down approaches. These algorithms allow the generation of generic information in a disaggregated way. However, they do not support the depiction of typical energy demand fluctuations in the LPs in any form. Furthermore, to thoroughly integrate possibilities to individualise and probabilistically diversify the depicted sites we developed a bottom-up algorithm complementing the other approaches.

Similar to our preceding study, typical characteristics of production processes like energy consumption per unit, production times etc. were assessed. Due to the mentioned process diversity of the non-energy intensive industries our research is only limited to the most energy intensive and (production-wise) dominating processes. Typically, we included three to four processes per NACE subsector in this algorithm.

Markov chains describe sequences of discrete states over time for single processes [29]. A Markovian transition matrix contains probabilities for the process to pass from a current state to the next one. Dock et al. [14] applied Markov chains for modelling an electric arc furnace for 40 different states resulting in a 40 by 40 transition matrix. The demand of all states was based on real-life load measurements.

Because our approach relies on process information from literature, we established 7 standardised states which we describe within dedicated Markovian transition matrices: Off, Ramp-up, Processing, Shutdown, Service, Failure and Stand-by. Swiderski et al. [30] similarly classify process states to evaluate machinery readiness and reliability and to identify optimisation measures. Our assessed processes can operate within these states by a predefined 7 by 7 transition matrix. However, the entries of this transition matrix are subject to change because the likelihood of a process to pass from state 1 (Off) to state 2 (Ramp-Up) varies depending on the current phase (e.g. non-production or production), which we described in Section 2.2. Therefore, the Markov model is not determined statically, but dynamically as a function of time as also described by Sandholtz et al. [31] for another field of application.

Fig. 6 explains the overall applied, dynamic Markov model and corresponding states for a selected process and for the most basic shift model (40 h/week). We added a transition phase (Fig. 6 (b) and (c) in yellow) to the existing production and non-production phases. This is because not all production processes are usually

turned on or off at the same time. Fig. 6 (b) shows that the production capacity during the production phase is at 100%, while during the non-production phase at 0%. To correctly model this behaviour, the states of all corresponding processes must be managed via four different transition matrices α , β , γ and δ Fig. 6 (a). Each of these matrices contains different transition probabilities for the processes, applied at different phases. For example, the probabilistic transition from Off to Ramp-Up in matrix α during non-production times is always 0%. However, in matrix β this probability is near 100%, because of a production start (other states during production start can be Failure and Service). Additionally, the model avoids forbidden state transitions like from Off to Shut down. It is noted that we applied this paradigm for production processes which are operated by personnel and therefore correlated to the given shift models. We found that processes like kilns, operated to dry woodchips or veneer wood over a longer period (NACE 16.1.0), operate mainly without personnel during non-production times [32]. These processes do not correlate to the given shift model, are continuously running and are therefore modelled with a single transition matrix which is equivalent to matrix γ . In both cases, shift-model independent and dependent, the matrix γ defines the production dynamic of the processes. The underlying data is based upon the overall operating time of each process in relation to the length of the production phase as well as Failure and Service probabilities from literature [30]. Regarding the transition between processes, we applied the simulation paradigm of discrete event simulation [33]. Here, a logical sequence of the production stream can be simulated. For example, in the subsector NACE 16.1.0, a typical energy intensive process sequence would be starting from wood logging, wood sawing and finishing of wood planks.

Fig. 6 (c) shows an example of the specific energy consumption (SEC) of a shift model correlated process over time. All other transitions in α are at 0% except for Off to Off, Off to Failure or Off to Service. In each of these cases, the SEC of this process is 0 kWh/t. In the first transition phase (yellow), the matrix β is applied which is for turning on the process. We assumed that the timely length of the transition phase is 30 min which, however, can be adapted freely by the user. During the production phase, the matrix γ is applied, while the second transition phase involves mainly Shutdown or Service states.

In conclusion, this applied Markov model contains four 7 by 7 transition matrices. For other, more complex shift models this number increases. Furthermore, when including shift breaks as

Fig. 6. (a) Transformation of the applied transition matrix according to the current production phase; (b) Plant production capacity as a function of time and current production phase; (c) Specific energy consumption of a selected process during different production phases. Here the process takes up various states (d) in accordance with the current transition matrix from (a). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

transition or non-production phases, more transition matrices must be added. This functionality is included in the software *Ganymed*.

2.4. Economy of scale - Regression model

The dynamic Markov model is applied to depict energy demand fluctuations of industrial processes. However, this does not finally constitute the finished LP. It is necessary to expand the resulting fluctuations' profile by the average energy consumption, which is typical for industrial sites in the chosen NACE subsector and with this size.

The IAC database provides information on electricity and direct fuel (e.g., natural gas, coal, oil etc. for thermal application) consumption of the investigated single sites. These energy carriers are termed final energy carriers at the plant border. Additionally, the IAC database contains the electricity peak demand for one selected month of the given fiscal year respectively. Both average consumption and peak demand are vital information to further refine the generated process-specific profile from Section 2.3 to a synthetic, site-specific LP as described in Section 2.5.

To correctly assess the average energy consumption of the generated site, the dependent variable must be linked to given, explanatory variables. As also production capacity of the single sites is given by the IAC database, we utilise the effect of Economy of Scales (EOS) to reason a correlation between the specific energy consumption (SEC) and the production capacity. EOS describes the dependency of applied production input factors on the produced output [34]. It mainly finds its use as an instrument in

microeconomics to express cost reduction effects when increasing production. Only a very small amount of studies practically apply this effect for assessing SEC: For example, Ironmonger et al. [35] show that EOS is applicable for residential households, where the SEC depends on the number of residents.

Fig. 7 shows the evaluated data for the subsector NACE 16.1.0 for production-specific electricity (a) and direct fuel (c) consumption. The observed data resembles the single industrial sites in the IAC database. The corresponding fit lines indicate the EOS effect [36]: A higher specific energy consumption can be observed at small production volumes. When the capacity increases, production becomes more efficient in terms of input consumption, which is energy in our case. This result is especially interesting as it can be observed for the different industrial sites of the specific subsectors in general. We further evaluated the fit functions by generating a corresponding double logarithmic plot of Fig. 7 (a) and (c) in (b) and (d). The observed linearity is a common proof to identify EOS in microeconomics [37]. The linear dependency of both logarithmically scaled variables can be expressed via the following function:

$$\text{Log}(c) = a - b \text{Log}(Q) \tag{2}$$

c represents the input factor per unit of capacity (e.g. cost [€/m³] or energy in our case [kWh/m³]) and Q the production capacity [m³] [37]. The production capacity can also be referred to as tonnes [t] or other units.

To thoroughly prove the statistical correlation of these EOS parameters in Fig. 7, we investigated the depicted relationship further by examining statistical indicators underlying the hypothesis of correlation between specific energy consumption and

Fig. 7. EOS effect of the subsector “NACE 16.1.0 – Sawmilling and planing of wood” for (a) specific electricity consumption, (b) double logarithmic plot of electricity consumption, (c) specific direct fuel consumption, (d) double logarithmic plot of direct fuel consumption.

production capacity [38]: Fig. 8 shows these evaluations for the depicted EOS correlations from Fig. 7 for electricity and direct fuel respectively. As the linearity of logarithmic data can clearly be observed in Fig. 7, the independence of residuals is investigated in Fig. 8(a) and (c) to prove that no relationship between the predicted values from the linear regression and its errors is existent. The hypothesis is met when the correlation factor r and the average of included residuals \bar{x} is approximately 0 [25]. For residuals of electricity data points these indicators equal $r = 0.000218$ and $\bar{x} = 0.000055$, for residuals of direct fuel data points $r = -0.081$ and $\bar{x} = -0.360$ respectively. It can be observed that these indicators of direct fuel data points deviate stronger from 0 than electricity data points. Besides the independency of errors, the normality of these residuals is further proof of a statistical linear relationship: Here, a normal probability plot includes the residuals of all data points in comparison to the z-value, which equals the multiplication factor of the standard deviation from the mean average of all residuals. The assumption of linearity is met, when the distribution of residuals is approximately normal, indicated by a linear relationship in these plots (as shown in Fig. 8 (b) and (d)). For both sets of data points (electricity and direct fuel), the last method indicates normal distribution successfully. At last, we investigated our hypothesis of normality by conducting a t-test, investigating the significance of the shown data for a significance level α of $\alpha = 0.05$. The test shows a P-value of $P = 5.608 \cdot 10^{-48}$ for electricity consumption and $P = 3.712 \cdot 10^{-31}$ for direct fuel consumption, which are both significantly lower than the significance level α . In conclusion, the assumption of the linear relationship between specific energy consumption and production capacity in a logarithmic context is proven, hence all relevant statistical indicators demonstrate satisfactory results.

Via these fit curves for each NACE subsector from Fig. 7, a typical specific electricity and direct fuel consumption for every industrial site with a specified size and sector can be assessed. The user-defined production capacity of the site (see Fig. 3 (a)) for which a synthetic LP should be generated, acts as an input parameter for the fit curves to calculate the corresponding SEC.

2.5. Load factor iteration algorithm & generation of final load profiles

In this last step of our proposed LP method, we combine the time-resolved energy demands reached from the dynamic Markov model and the determined real-life plant-specific energy consumptions and demands from the EOS model, as Fig. 9 shows. The main goal is to calibrate the baseload of the energy demand profiles from the Markov model (Fig. 9 (a)), mainly covering the energy intensive process demands during production phases. We managed this by utilising the stochastically determined industry and site-specific energy consumptions and demands from the EOS regression model (Fig. 9 (b)), as described in Section 2.4.

The backbone of this calibration step is the calculation of an underlying load factor (LF) for the site, which originates from the EOS regression model. The LF ranges from 0 to 1 and is typically calculated for electricity, but can be applied for direct fuel too [39]. It, therefore, offers important insights into the assumed shape of LPs as the energy demand of consumers with lower load factors fluctuates stronger than that of consumers with higher ones. The load factor is calculated through:

$$LF = \frac{E}{P \cdot t} \quad (3)$$

As the ratio is calculated of E as energy consumption [kWh] to P as peak demand [kW] in the time frame t [h].

The peak demand for both electricity and direct fuel is to be determined in the next step. However, the calculation of both parameters varies. While monthly industrial electricity consumption is rather constant throughout the year, monthly direct fuel consumption presents itself as a function of ambient temperature [10]. However, the demand for both electricity and direct fuel fluctuates, as already explained in Section 2.3, due to changing process states.

2.5.1. Determination of the scaled electricity peak

In terms of electricity, the IAC database contains information on the peak demand for a selected month in the given fiscal year of all surveyed sites. Because consumption is measured

Fig. 8. Statistical proof of assumptions of EOS correlation of the subsector “NACE 16.1.0 – Sawmilling and planing of wood”: (a) Residual plot of electricity consumption, (b) Normal probability plot of electricity consumption data points, (c) Residual plot of direct fuel consumption, (d) Normal probability plot of direct fuel consumption data points.

Fig. 9. Workflow of the combination of dynamic Markov model (a) and EOS regression model (b) within load factor iteration (c).

in kWh and peak demand in kW, a linear relationship of both parameters is given. *Ganymed* generates linear fit functions for all observed data points of the corresponding NACE subsectors. By determining the electricity consumption from the EOS model in the first step, the peak demand can be assessed next, by applying the following linear equation:

$$E = m \cdot P + b \tag{4}$$

With E as energy consumption [kWh], m as slope [h], P as peak demand [kW] and b as intercept [kWh].

For determining the electricity peak, we neglect ambient temperature variations, unlike direct fuel peaks (see the section below).

2.5.2. Determination of the scaled direct fuel peak

Direct fuel demand is not constant over a year. Unlike the electricity demand, a share of the direct fuel demand of industrial sites is influenced by ambient temperature. Jesper et al. [10] proved this through an extensive industrial LP analysis. This ambient temperature-dependent share mainly originates from space heating or air conditioning appliances and is more distinctive during winter months, as Fig. 10 (a) and (b) show. The other part of direct fuel demand is attributable to thermal energy for process heat and is therefore rather constant throughout the year [40]. Statistic’s Austria [24] states these shares of non-ambient temperature-dependent and ambient temperature-dependent thermal energy for each industrial subsector. Throughout this information, the assessed direct fuel consumption from the EOS model can be separated accordingly.

The non-ambient temperature-dependent demand is calculated similarly to the assessment of the electricity peak, see 2.5.1. Regarding the share of direct fuel demand, which is ambient temperature dependent, we utilised the *SigLinDe* function for the calculation [41]. Here, the ambient temperature T_{Amb} acts as an input for *SigLinDe* to calculate a multiplication factor h for the

Fig. 10. Yearly direct fuel demand, divided into ambient temperature-dependent consumption and process-specific consumption.

Fig. 11. Iteration of unscaled LP from the Markov model to generate the finished (scaled) LP.

corrected direct fuel consumption. For an ambient temperature of 8 °C the multiplication factor is set to 1 on default. The factor is larger than 1 for temperatures under 8 °C and smaller than 1 for temperatures above 8 °C. The underlying regression function of *SigLinDe* is a mixed linear and Sigmoid function [41]. We implemented an hourly-resolved temperature profile of Austria for one year. However, *Ganymed* also allows the implementation of other temperature profiles as well as the selection of the month, for which the LP shall be generated. The adapted direct fuel consumption E_{SLD} per hour can then be calculated via

$$E_{SLD} = E \cdot h(T_{Amb.}) \cdot F_{WT} \tag{5}$$

with E as average natural gas consumption [kWh] per hour, which is the share subtracted as explained above, and F_{WT} as a factor of the associated day of the week in correlation with the shift model. The overall direct fuel peak demand is calculated via the sum of both hourly peaks (ambient temperature dependent and non-ambient temperature dependent). With this information, the direct fuel LF from equation (3) can be assessed.

2.5.3. Load factor iteration

Based on the given information, *Ganymed* calculates the load factor for electricity and direct fuel to scale the given LPs from the Markov model. These LPs mainly contain information on the main contributions to the energy demand, originating from selected processes. However, these still show a certain grade of deviation compared to the finished LP. This is because smaller units and

general base loads (e.g., ventilation, lighting, base loads from smaller appliances and processes, ...) are neglected in the Markov model. By iterating the LPs from the Markov model to meet the assessed load factors (see Sections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2) this lack of information can be bypassed. As we mentioned in Section 1.1, a similar method is applied by Starke and Alkadi [42] for electricity demands. In this study, however, the unscaled load profile is based on standardised LPs.

Fig. 11 shows a simplified, iterative scaling of an LP with n iterative steps. The target LF can either be smaller or higher than the LF from the Markov model. Our algorithm fixates the established peak (determined according to Sections 2.5.1 and 2.5.2) and lowers or raises the residual demands to be in accordance with previously determined LF (and therefore overall energy consumption) in the considered time period. To do so, after each iterative step, an integral is calculated to assess the new area under the LP, which is equivalent to the energy consumption. If the current consumption corresponds to the assessed consumption (in other words, when $LF_{unscaled} == LF_{scaled}$) from the EOS model, the iteration is ended. Furthermore, the user can specify a different load factor instead of the one from the EOS model through the *Ganymed* GUI at any time.

Throughout this chain of algorithms, an LP for electricity and/or direct fuel can be generated. The *Ganymed* GUI offers a simple step-by-step menu to synthesise a fictitious or existing industrial plant quickly and efficiently.

Table 2

Information on the selected five case studies. This input data is applied in the developed algorithm in Ganymed.

Case number	NACE subsector	Number of employees	Production capacity
Case 1	10.8.5 – Manufacture of prepared meals and dishes	36	0.9 t/h
Case 2	22.2.2 – Manufacture of plastic packing goods	49	1.8 t/h
Case 3	27.1.1 – Manufacture of electric motors, generators and transformers	7	0.05 t/h
Case 4	31.0.1 – Manufacture of office and shop furniture	4	0.08 t/h
Case 5	25.5.0 – Forging, pressing, stamping and roll-forming of metal; powder metallurgy	21	0.5 t/h

Table 3

Underlying energy intensive processes and literature sources in each case study.

Case number	Energy intensive production process	Literature sources
Case 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grading unit • Grinding unit • Cooking tunnel 	[44–46]
Case 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw material shredder • Forming unit • Extruder 	[47–49]
Case 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wiring process • Forming unit • Assembling process 	[50]
Case 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vacuum unit • Side spindle • Assembling process 	[51,52]
Case 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heating unit • Forging process • Deburring process 	[53,54]

3. Validation of developed method

3.1. Case descriptions

We validated the developed methodology by conducting various case studies, of which five will be presented in this study. The presented data for this study's validation process is published by Braeuer [43]. Each case represents a real-life manufacturing plant from Germany and contains information on its industrial subsector, company size and production capacity as well as real-life measured, 15-min resolved yearly electricity LPs. The validation of direct fuel LPs is not part of this publication, because of data protection regulations of partaking companies.

Through personal correspondence, further information on the industrial plants was assessed as shown in Table 2. This data acts as input for the developed method. The LPs generated with Ganymed are validated by comparison with the real measured LPs of each corresponding NACE subsector. We selected these five cases to represent the broadest possible application for all non-energy intensive industries.

The information on energy intensive production processes as input for the dynamic Markov model, specific for all selected cases, was based upon different literature sources as Table 3 shows.

Overall, Fig. 12 gives an overview of the data flow for the conducted five case studies starting from input parameters in Tables 2 and 3 to the outputted LPs and follow-up evaluation and analysis. The utilised databases are not shown in this figure. Overall, the selected industrial subsector and the defined number of employees from Table 2 act as input parameters for the shift model calculator. Data of energy intensive production processes from Table 3 in combination with the identified shift model initiate the generation of the unscaled LPs. The Economy of Scale regression model calculates representative load factors based on the information on production capacity from Table 2. These load factors then scale the already generated LP to bridge the gap of unknown additional processes in each case.

3.2. Results and discussion

We modelled each case in Ganymed along the outlined data flow described in Fig. 12: Because the number of employees for each case is given deterministically in Table 2, the stochastic calculation via power function fit from Section 2.1 was not executed. The algorithm determined the most applicable shift model as described in Section 2.2 for cases 1 to 5 as follows: A 8 h/day (40 h/week) shift for cases 1, 3 and 4, a 24 h/6 days (144 h/week) shift for case 2 and a 16 h/5 days (80 h/week) shift for case 5. We generated electricity LPs for all five case studies based on the identified shift models and the information on energy intensive processes to feed the dynamic Markov model.

As mentioned in Section 2.5 the yearly electricity demand for an industrial plant can be described as mostly independent of ambient temperature. Thus, we overlaid 52 weekly LPs (52 weeks/year) from each of the measured plants for validating the synthetic LP. Fig. 13 shows these 52 weekly LPs in blue as well as their average LP in red for the selected case 1. The generated, synthetic LP is shown in black. The demand is depicted in 675 single 15-min values per LP. Furthermore, we deemed this interval as suitable due to the correlation with the energy market, as intraday trading is conducted at a minimum of quarter-hour intervals [55].

We validated the deviation of the synthetic LP from the measured ones by generating boxplots and calculating the mean-average-percentage-error (MAPE) for each case. We used each boxplot diagram in Fig. 14, corresponding to each case study, to evaluate the deviation of the synthetic LP (shown as single line indicators) to the measured data in the boxes. Through this, the magnitude of the deviation can be analysed. In overall, the middle line of the single boxes indicates the median of all values. The bottom and top edges of the boxes show the lower and upper quartiles of all data points. Thus, 50% of all data points lie within the box. Both whiskers of every box indicate the last data point, which is not declared as an outlier anymore (<1.5 times the interquartile range/box length starting from the boxes' edge).

The grey boxes exhibit the overall average demands for each of the 52 measured LPs. We compare this with the average demand of the synthetic LP, shown as single line indicators to the right of the grey boxes. The following boxes (light yellow, green, blue, red) in each boxplot contain the 52 data points during a selected time. We agreed upon selecting four chronological 15-min time stamps: the 10th hour in the week, the 37.5th hour in the week, the 75th hour in the week and the 105th hour in the week. In the examination of the results, we focus on the most prominent time of production, which is the weekdays from Monday to Friday. For this, we evenly distributed the marked time stamps as described above within the weekdays and neglected the distinct evaluation during weekends. Each of the coloured boxes is then compared to the corresponding point-in-time in the synthetic LP, again shown as single line indicators. Additionally, Fig. 13 shows these time stamps.

Regarding the mean-average-percentage-error (MAPE) based analysis, we applied the following equation:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{P_m - P_s}{P_m} \right| * 100\% \quad (6)$$

Fig. 12. Data flow from input parameters to outputted LPs for all case studies.

Fig. 13. Comparison of weekly measured electricity LPs of one year (blue) and averaged measured LP (red) with synthetic, generated LP (black). The marked time stamps (light yellow, green, blue, red) correspond to the boxplot in Fig. 14. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

As $n = 675$ represents the total number of data points per LP, P_m constitutes the measured and P_s the electricity demand of the synthetic LP at each time stamp (hour of the week) t .

The resulting MAPEs are included in Table 4. Additionally, we evaluated the deviation of the maximum peak and minimum

demand between the average (measured) and the synthetic LP similarly to formula (5).

The synthetic LPs in cases 1 and 2 show on average a good approximation to the measured LPs, especially regarding the deviation of minimum demand. The peak demand varies slightly

Fig. 14. Boxplot diagrams for evaluating the deviation of the synthetic LPs (single line indicators) compared to the measured data (boxes). All boxes include 52 data points (as of 52 weeks per year) for different times in the LP. For all five boxplots case 1 is shown in (a), case 2 in (b), case 3 in (c), case 4 in (d) and case 5 in (e).

Table 4
Resulting MAPEs, deviation of maximum peak and minimum demand between average (measured) and synthetic LP for all five cases.

Case number	MAPE	Deviation peak demand	Deviation minimum demand
Case 1	19%	11%	2%
Case 2	11%	30%	4%
Case 3	35%	17%	7%
Case 4	644%	345%	57%
Case 5	29%	26%	49%

more, possibly because the average (measured) LPs fluctuate less due to the arithmetical calculation, which can also be observed for case 1 from the red curve in Fig. 13. Case 1 exhibits a sufficient approximation with low deviation at different time stamps too, which is shown in Fig. 14 (a). The overall data point variance is higher in case 2. Nevertheless, all synthetic time stamps align with the boxes satisfactorily (Fig. 14 (b)).

Case 3 shows a higher MAPE, however, slightly less deviation regarding maximum and minimum peak, possibly due to higher fluctuations of the synthetic LP. This can also be observed in Fig. 14 (c) as the demand during each of the four single time stamps lies outside the boxes of the boxplot. This variance probably results from generating the LP at very low power levels. We will explain this effect in the following paragraph for case 4.

The modelled and measured results of case 4 vary dramatically with an overall MAPE of 644%. During the execution of our case studies, we experienced major deviations between measured and synthetic LPs at low energy peak demands under 200 kW. We found that the linear relationship between peak demand and consumption (as we indicated in Section 2.5.1) exhibits large error rates in some NACE subsectors at these low demands. Often, the linearity remains inconclusive in these areas. This leads to the fact that the algorithm estimates higher peak demands. This results in major deviations between the measured and synthetic LPs. We originally found this incidence in cases 3 and 4. We modified the algorithm to process a non-linear fit, when the variation of

Fig. 15. DFT stem plots and corresponding amplitudes for (a) synthetic LP and (b) average (measured) LP of case 1. The following segments are highlighted in (a) and (b): (I) – Higher fluctuations of the synthetic LP in a short-term manner, (II) – Strong dominance of the signal with 24 h periodicity, (III) – Higher amplitude for a weekly fluctuation in measured LP. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the linearity increases at low demand levels. Based on this non-linear fitting function the adjusted peak demand is forwarded to LP generation. This modification exhibits valid results in case 3. However, case 4, which is located in another NACE subsector, is not afflicted by these changes. Case 4 shows the limitations of our model. For these cases, the execution of a sole bottom-up approach, which we developed in our previous work [5], may be more advisable.

Case 5, again, exhibits acceptable results. The minimal demands of the synthetic LP are slightly lower than in the measured LPs, which can also be observed in Fig. 14 (e).

In cases 1, 3, 4 and 5, where the applied shift model indicates a significantly lower or no production during weekends, the measured LPs nevertheless show a slight increase in the electricity demand during Saturdays. We could not assume the reason for this.

In the next step, we performed a Discrete Fourier Transformation (DFT) analysis of the average (measured) and the synthetic LPs of all cases to evaluate these mentioned and further periodical features. The DFT decomposes any given input signal into a sum of periodic sine and cosine components, for which frequency, amplitude and phase can be assessed. Groß [56], for example, examined yearly electricity residual loads by conducting a DFT with the means of analysing their periodical potential for i.e. long-, mid- or short-term storage.

Fig. 15 shows the DFT analysis for case 1 of (a) the synthetic LP and (b) the average (measured) LP. We highlighted three comparable segments. The first segment (I), representing short-time fluctuations, exhibits higher DFT amplitudes of the synthetic LPs indicating stronger fluctuations with those periodicities. As we already mentioned, due to the arithmetic calculation, the

average (measured) LP tends to show less rapidly alternating fluctuations. This can also be seen in Fig. 13 by comparing the red and black coloured LPs, especially during non-production phases. Overall, the definition of 15-min intervals tends to inflict less strong fluctuations within the overall LP than for smaller intervals (e.g. 1- or 10-min) [57]. This is due to the calculated average within these intervals. A strong dominance of a daily periodicity can be observed in both plots in the second segment (II). The observed amplitudes reach very similar values. This also exemplifies the applied 8 h/day (40 h/week) shift model as a high changing rate of the LP during working days is present. The most distinctive difference between measured and modelled LPs can be noted in the third segment (III). Here, the amplitude of the measured LP at weekly periodicity is significantly higher than in our synthetic model. This underlines the presence of weekend loads (especially Saturday), which we can currently not depict within our model. As we also evaluated the results from DFT for cases 3, 4 and 5, we found the same weekly, long-term dominance in the DFT amplitude being more thoroughly developed in the measured LPs.

4. Conclusions & outlook

As we established a well-functioning, bottom-up model for generating load profiles (LPs) for energy intensive industries in our preceding study [5], we now present a combined top-down and bottom-up algorithm to cover the remaining non-energy intensive subsectors. Through this, we are closing the gap by incorporating the whole industrial sector to create, to our knowledge, the first comprehensive software for generating timely

high-resolved, synthetic energy demand and generation profiles, called *Ganymed*.

To conclude our study, we reflect on our hypotheses stated in Section 1.2:

- The non-energy intensive industrial subsectors outnumber the energy intensive industries regarding employment, gross value added and produced products as we showed in Section 2. These more comprehensive subsectors demand a wider range of implemented methods for generating LPs rather than a sole bottom-up approach. Also, existing methodologies lack the assessment of multi-energy carriers without the need for extensive databases. In our first hypothesis in Section 1.2, we situated that a combined bottom-up and top-down approach will adequately depict the non-energy intensive industries on a multi-energy level without extensive process-specific data. We, therefore, developed a mixed methodology with top-down methods incorporating real-life plant data and a bottom-up algorithm for implementing the timely resolution of process energy demands into the overall methodology.
- To prove our second hypothesis, we built on the expertise of Hernández et al. [18], who outlined the dependency between working days, weekends and holidays in industry and electrical LPs. We showed that production and non-production times during working days need to be interlinked for the generation of multi-energy LPs in form of concrete, well-defined shift models. Moreover, thermal LPs are not only influenced by the hour of the day but also by the ambient temperature, which needs to be considered in LP generation. We showed this dependency in Section 2.5.2.
- The consideration of the most energy intensive processes within a non-energy intensive plant will suffice for generating industrial LPs. As we already stated this finding in our preceding study [5], we now apply this fact in our developed methodology. A representative LP can be generated by calibrating the remaining peak demand and the base load via existing real-life plant data. This also changes the need to gather extensive process-specific data for depicting multi-energy carriers within bottom-up approaches.
- From a top-down point of view, the dependency between the specific energy consumption of industrial plants and production capacity can clearly not be described linearly. It constitutes itself via a logarithmic function. Thus, this effect indicates that the microeconomics' paradigm of Economy of Scale practically affects the energy system as well. Therefore, we described the specific energy consumption of industrial plants of different subsectors as logarithmic fit functions in relationship to the production capacity.

At last, the results of the presented methodology exhibit satisfactory approximations in depicting real-life production facilities with an overall mean percentage error of around 20% for plants with weekly peak demand higher than 200 kW. However, we found that the demand of smaller consumers (< 200 kW) often differs from the results in our approach, even after corrections in our algorithm have been made. We assume that this deviation results from a higher heterogeneity of the daily work and included processes in small facilities. As we described in our preceding study, a sole bottom-up approach might be more advisable here. When analysing the periodicities of the synthetic LPs, we found more fluctuations with higher frequencies and a weaker dominance of weekly periodicities when compared to measured LPs. The first feature is probably due to the comparison with an average, measured LP. The second one reveals the necessity of including load behaviour on weekends in the algorithm, which could not have been approached until now due to limited access to information on industrial shift models.

As we strive for developing our model further, we will optimise certain features and algorithms in the future. Firstly, we will enlarge our existing, incorporated databases. Secondly, we will enhance our EOS model and the iterative load factor algorithm to assess peak demands more thoroughly. In this regard, energy economic paradigms like time-of-use can potentially further improve the generation of LPs in this methodology.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paul Josef Binderbauer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Aaron Keuschnig:** Methodology, Validation, Data curation. **Thomas Kienberger:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

Table 5
Summary table comparing current study with past research.

	Objective	Subsectors (IEA)	Energy carrier	Approach	Solving method	Constraints
[9]	Generating synthetic industrial LPs	5 (Food, Beverages & Tobacco; Machinery; Iron & Steel; Non-Ferrous Metals; Non-Metallic Minerals)	Electricity	Top-Down	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based upon normalised LPs from literature • Divided into energy end uses • Applying fluctuation to generated LPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solely based upon normalised profiles • No process-specific data available
[10]	Investigating the dependency between heat profiles and ambient temperature	6 (Food, Beverages & Tobacco; Chemical & Petrochemical; Iron & Steel; Machinery; Automotive; Non-Metallic Minerals)	Natural gas/Heat load	Top-Down	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normalising the data • k-means clustering of measured LPs • Regression analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive data necessary • High aggregation level

(continued on next page)

Table 5 (continued).

	Objective	Subsectors (IEA)	Energy carrier	Approach	Solving method	Constraints
[11]	DSM measures for medium-sized industries	3 (Iron & Steel; Chemical & Petrochemical; Food, Beverages & Tobacco)	Electricity	Top-Down	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • k-means clustering of compartments of measured LPs • Investigating similarities • Derivation of operating and scheduling modes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive data necessary • High aggregation level
[12]	Investigating DSM potential of paper and food industries	2 (Pulp & Paper; Food, Beverages & Tobacco)	Electricity	Top-Down	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normalising the data • k-means clustering of measured LPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive data necessary • High aggregation level • Limited subsectoral investigation
[13]	Generating synthetic industrial LPs for market-oriented operation of power systems	2 (Machinery; Food, Beverages & Tobacco)	Electricity	Top-Down	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical analysis and derivation of load shape factors of measured LPs • Fuzzy c-means clustering of monthly generated LPs • Combining the clustering results in general LPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilisation of data from only 18 different industrial plants
[14]	Modelling of synthetic LPs of real life production plant	1 (Iron & Steel)	Electricity, Natural gas/Heat load	Bottom-Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement at site • Modelling of measured LP via Markov chains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only applicable at the specific site • Measurements necessary
[15]	Optimisation of manufacturing scheduling and DSM potential	3 (Pulp & Paper; Machinery; Chemical & Petrochemical)	Electricity, Natural gas/Heat load	Bottom-Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy system assessment at site • Modelling of singular processes • Generating LPs on various systemic levels • Integration in further economic investigations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive data necessary • Complex methodology including various parameters
[5]	Generating synthetic industrial LPs of energy intensive subsectors	5 (Iron & Steel; Pulp & Paper; Chemical & Petrochemical; Non-Metallic Minerals; Non-Ferrous Metals)	Electricity, Natural gas/Heat load	Bottom-Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection of process-specific literature data • Integration in discrete event simulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only applicable for production route itself
This Study	Generating synthetic industrial LPs of non-energy intensive subsectors	7 (Wood & Wood Products; Machinery; Food, Beverages & Tobacco; Mining & Quarrying; Automotive; Textiles & Leather; Non-Ferrous Metals)	Electricity, Natural gas/Heat load	Top-Down and Bottom-Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stochastic analyses of industrial databases • Fits for employee number, energy demand and production shifts • Energy intensive processes depicted by Markov model • Combination of top-down and bottom-up approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited to databases • Outliers of daily shifts possible

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